

TEMPORAL VARIATION IN ARRIVAL AND PRICES OF PIGEON PEA IN MAJOR MARKETS OF INDIA

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Abstract

This study examines the variations in arrivals and prices of Pigeon Pea (*Cajanus cajan*) in five major Indian markets Latur, Bijapur, Ujjain, Agra, and Rajkot from 2014 to 2023. Utilizing secondary data and quantitative methods, including Compound Growth Rate (CGR), Coefficient of Variation (CV), Cuddy-Della Valle Instability Index (CDVI), and correlation analysis, the research reveals significant disparities in growth rates and market stability. Key findings indicate that Latur and Agra experienced minimal to negative growth in arrivals, while Bijapur faced supply constraints despite rising prices. High price variability was observed, particularly in Ujjain. The analysis shows a prevailing inverse relationship between arrivals and prices across most markets. The results underscore the need for strategic interventions to enhance supply stability and mitigate price volatility in the Pigeon Pea sector. Future research should explore underlying factors and targeted solutions to improve market resilience.

Keywords: Pigeon Pea, Temporal Variation, Arrival, Prices, Market Stability, Price Volatility, Supply Constraints, Instability Index, Inverse Relationship,

Introduction

The introduction establishes the context for this research on Pigeon Pea (*Cajanus cajan*), a crucial pulse crop in India that serves as a vital protein source for millions. Thriving in semi-arid regions, it plays a key role in food security and agricultural sustainability. India is the largest producer and consumer of Pigeon Pea, but market fluctuations caused by seasonal variations, climatic conditions, and policies like the Minimum Support Price (MSP) impact farmer incomes and market stability.

This study aims to analyze the temporal variations in the arrivals and prices of Pigeon Pea in major Indian markets, focusing on trends, seasonal and cyclical indices, and the relationship between supply and prices. Insights from this research will help stakeholders including farmers, traders, and policymakers make informed decisions, mitigate market inefficiencies, and promote fair pricing.

The scope of this research encompasses five key markets: Latur, Bijapur, Ujjain, Agra, and Rajkot, covering a decade from 2013-2023. By employing quantitative methods and analyzing secondary data, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of market dynamics. Despite some limitations, including reliance on historical data and regional variability, the findings aim to support better decision-making and enhance market stability for Pigeon Pea.

The specific objectives of the study are:

- To study Trends and Variations in Arrival and Prices of Pigeon Pea.
- To study the relationship between Arrival and Prices of Pigeon Pea.

Materials and methods

1. Source of Data

The study is based on secondary data sourced from www.agmarknet.com and the Directorate of Pulses.

2. Area of Study

The analysis focuses on five major pigeon pea markets in India: Latur (Maharashtra), Bijapur (Karnataka), Ujjain (Madhya Pradesh), Agra (Uttar Pradesh), and Rajkot (Gujarat).

3. Period of Study

Monthly time series data on arrivals and prices were collected from 2013-14 to 2022-23.

Table 1. Compound Growth Rate in Arrival and Prices of Major Markets of India (2014-2023)

Major markets	Arrival		Prices	
	CGR	t value	CGR	t value
Latur	0.55	0.59	0.53**	2.71

4. Analytical Tools

4.1 Trends and Variations in Arrival and Prices

a. Compound Growth Rate (CGR): The exponential function $y = ab^t$ as used to estimate CGR, where y represents arrivals or prices, a is the intercept, and b is the growth coefficient. The CGR is calculated as:

$$\text{CGR} (\%) = [\text{Antilog} (\log b) - 1] \times 100$$

b. Coefficient of Variation (CV): CV measures variability to assess the stability of arrivals and prices. It is computed as:

$$\text{CV} (\%) = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

c. Cuddy-Della Valle Instability Index (CDVI): Used to measure instability, CDVI adjusts CV by the coefficient of determination R^2 :

$$\text{CDVI} (\%) = \text{CV} \times \sqrt{(1 - R^2)}$$

4.2 Relationship Between Arrival and Prices

Correlation Coefficient (r): The correlation between arrivals and prices is calculated using:

$$r = \frac{\text{Cov}(x,y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

where $\text{Cov}(x,y)$ is the covariance between arrivals and prices, and σ_x, σ_y are the standard deviations of arrivals and prices, respectively.

Result and discussion

Trends and variation in arrival and prices.

Compound Growth Rate (CGR):

Table 1. the compound growth rates (CGR) in pigeon pea arrivals and prices across major markets from 2014-2023 reveal varied trends. Latur showed minimal growth in arrivals (0.55%) with insignificant change, but prices increased moderately (0.53%) with significance. Bijapur saw a decline in arrivals (-1.82%) but a notable price rise (0.78%), indicating supply constraints. Ujjain displayed negligible growth in both arrivals (0.13%) and prices (0.02%), reflecting market stability. Agra experienced a significant drop in arrivals (-3.05%) while prices surged (1.08%), likely due to supply shortages. Rajkot recorded the highest growth in both arrivals (2.88%) and prices (0.75%), suggesting a healthy supply-demand balance. Overall, the results indicate that markets with declining or stagnant arrivals saw price increases, while Rajkot exhibited strong growth in both aspects.

Bijapur	-1.82	-1.44	0.78***	4.01
Ujjain	0.13	0.07	0.02	0.04
Agra	-3.05**	-2.86	1.08***	6.01
Rajkot	2.88***	4.04	0.75***	4.37

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significance at 1, 5 and 10 per cent, respectively.

Coefficient of variation

Table 2. Coefficient of variation in Arrival of Pigeon Pea in Major Markets of India (2014-2023)

Markets	Latur		Bijapur		Ujjain		Agra		Rajkot	
	Arrival		Arrival		Arrival		Arrival		Arrival	
	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)
2014	508.39	139.6	380.44	153.5	0.8	91	691.13	59.92	224.08	83.47
2015	1676.9	80.73	1700	258.69	38.46	248.48	574.79	83.65	158.7	94.39
2016	2092.3	59.23	539.55	270.09	0.2	54.77	-	-	550.13	99.39
2017	5205.2	73.23	490.25	105.23	2.13	63.78	834.45	35.69	1066.7	54.3
2018	4884.6	96.94	154.17	93.22	1.51	89.46	521.54	23.65	676.76	85.66
2019	2988.8	103.3	102.5	127.36	1.15	88.32	156.54	75.4	498.95	76.46
2020	3102.5	103.1	357.25	125.72	0.2	70.71	48.35	60.9	448.83	66.48
2021	4119.2	74.93	360.83	222.89	34.9	280.3	36.14	71.55	1024.9	119.2
2022	3078	85.47	219.6	141.84	31.07	219.96	488.13	79.67	1387.6	75.16
2023	1704.6	87.88	127.67	180.7	68.6	199.42	928.5	42.25	801.88	86.5
Avg	2936.03	86.34	443.23	203.62	17.90	225.25	475.51	53.06	683.85	83.07

In table 2. the coefficient of variation (CV) for pigeon pea arrivals across markets from 2014 to 2023 shows significant variability. Latur experienced moderate to high fluctuation in arrivals (CV: 59.23%-139.57%), indicating inconsistent supply. Bijapur had the highest instability, with CV values exceeding 100% in most years, pointing to unpredictable arrivals. Ujjain also showed high variability (CV: 54.77%-

280.3%), reflecting its unstable market conditions. Agra displayed lower variability, with a more stable supply in recent years (CV: 23.65%-83.65%). Rajkot exhibited relatively more stability (CV: 54.3%-119.24%) and higher mean arrivals, indicating a more consistent market compared to others. Overall, Bijapur and Ujjain showed the greatest supply fluctuations, while Rajkot was the most stable.

Table 3. Coefficient of variation in Prices of Pigeon Pea in Major Markets of India (2014-2023)

Markets	Latur		Bijapur		Ujjain		Agra		Rajkot	
	Prices		Prices		Prices		Prices		Prices	
	Mean (Rs)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs)	CV (%)
2014	4731.7	5.35	3974.33	9.77	2834.6	23.66	4579.9	6.91	4069.1	7.55
2015	8201.4	25	6300.33	23.42	4236.6	36.65	6623.8	16.58	7289.8	21.37
2016	7836.8	19.61	7106.55	20.77	6548.6	21.77	-	-	6902.1	17.85
2017	4139.8	8.63	3863.83	9.89	2826.3	21.36	3624.8	7.63	3601.2	8.05
2018	3967.3	9.28	3732.83	10.48	2615.3	14.2	3497.4	8.97	3805.8	9.06
2019	5334.8	4.79	5173.5	4.36	3557.3	21.18	4752.8	9.25	4973.3	4.66
2020	5247.2	7.32	5115.92	10.47	3050.3	17.49	4962.4	11.91	5280.7	8.93
2021	6323.9	4.95	6043.33	6.49	3132.4	24.73	5837.3	7.46	5886.3	6.33
2022	6739.5	8.49	6083.7	10.16	3645.1	40.89	6508.6	2.15	6099.1	7.02
2023	9270.1	12.54	9073.17	22.84	4884.5	43.31	7558.7	14.53	8636.1	14.62
Avg	6179.25	11.74	5646.75	14.09	3733.09	27.57	5327.30	9.82	5654.35	11.49

Table 3. shows the coefficient of variation (CV) for pigeon pea prices from 2014 to 2023 reveals that Ujjain and Bijapur experienced the highest price volatility, with CV values frequently exceeding 20%, reflecting significant instability. Latur and Rajkot showed more price stability, with lower CV values generally ranging between 4.66% and

25%, though Rajkot saw some fluctuations in recent years. Agra had moderate variability, with stable prices in certain years but occasional volatility, particularly in 2023. Overall, Ujjain and Bijapur were the most unstable markets, while Latur and Rajkot demonstrated better price consistency.

Cuddy-Della Valle Instability Index (CDVI):

Table 4. CDVI (Cuddy-Della Valle Index) of Arrival and Prices of Pigeon Pea in Major Markets of India (2014-2023)

Markets	Arrival			Prices		
	CV (%)	R ²	CDVI	CV (%)	R ²	CDVI
Latur	86.34	0.003	86.21	11.74	0.06	11.37
Bijapur	203.62	0.02	201.59	14.09	0.13	13.10

Ujjain	225.25	5.9E-05	225.24	27.57	2.177E-05	27.57
Agra	53.06	0.08	51.01	9.82	0.27	8.42
Rajkot	83.07	0.12	77.80	11.49	0.14	10.65

In table 4. the Cuddy-Della Valle Index (CDVI) analysis from 2014 to 2023 reveals significant instability in pigeon pea arrivals and prices across major markets. Ujjain exhibited the highest instability for arrivals (CDVI: 225.24%) and prices (CDVI: 27.57%), indicating substantial fluctuations. Bijapur also showed considerable instability in arrivals (CDVI: 201.59%) and moderate volatility in prices (CDVI: 13.10%). In

contrast, Agra demonstrated the most stability in both arrivals (CDVI: 51.01%) and prices (CDVI: 8.42%), while Rajkot and Latur had relatively lower instability overall. These results suggest that Ujjain and Bijapur are more susceptible to supply shocks, whereas Agra benefits from a more stable market environment.

The relationship between arrival and prices of Pigeon Pea.

Table 5. Relationship between Arrival and Prices of Pigeon Pea in Major Markets of India (2014-2023)

Sr. no	Correlation Coefficient					
	Year	Latur	Bijapur	Ujjain	Agra	Rajkot
1	2014	-0.60*	0.37	-0.13	-0.64*	-0.60*
2	2015	-0.52	-0.46	-0.82***	-0.46	-0.31
3	2016	0.31	-0.55	-0.46	NA	0.56
4	2017	0.42	0.84***	0.21	0.15	0.62*
5	2018	0.50	0.33	0.72**	-0.50	0.40
6	2019	-0.05	-0.53	-0.56	-0.72**	-0.05
7	2020	-0.61*	-0.46	0.43	0.24	-0.68**
8	2021	0.48	-0.39	-0.55	-0.51	0.25
9	2022	-0.85***	-0.15	-0.49	0.71**	-0.53
10	2023	-0.87***	-0.55	-0.77***	-0.85***	-0.75**

Table 5. presents the correlation analysis of pigeon pea arrivals and prices from 2014 to 2023 reveals notable trends across major markets. Latur exhibited a strong negative correlation, particularly in 2014 (-0.60) and 2023 (-0.87), indicating that higher arrivals corresponded with lower prices. Bijapur exhibited a notable positive correlation in 2017 (0.84***), contrasting with moderate negative correlations in other years. Ujjain demonstrated the most substantial negative correlations in 2015 (-0.82***) and 2023 (-0.77***), reinforcing the inverse relationship. Agra displayed mixed results, with a significant positive correlation in 2022 (0.71**) and a negative correlation in 2014 (-0.64*). Rajkot generally had a negative relationship, especially in 2020 (-0.68**) and 2023 (-0.75**). Overall, most markets showed an inverse relationship between arrivals and prices, particularly in Ujjain and Latur, suggesting that local demand and supply conditions significantly influence market dynamics.

Conclusion

This study comprehensively examined the trends and relationships between pigeon pea arrivals and prices in major Indian markets from 2014 to 2023. The analysis revealed significant variations in the compound growth rates across markets, with Latur and Agra experiencing minimal to negative growth in arrivals, while Bijapur demonstrated supply constraints despite rising prices. The coefficient of variation highlighted substantial fluctuations, particularly in Bijapur and Ujjain, indicating instability in arrivals. Price variability was notably high in Ujjain and Bijapur, whereas Latur and Rajkot maintained better price consistency.

Furthermore, the Cuddy-Della Valle Index indicated that Ujjain and Bijapur were particularly susceptible to supply shocks, while Agra benefited from a more stable market environment. The correlation analysis underscored a prevailing inverse relationship between arrivals and prices across most markets, especially in Latur and Ujjain, reinforcing the classic supply-demand dynamics at play. Overall, the findings emphasize the necessity for market participants to adopt strategic measures to enhance supply stability, mitigate price volatility, and optimize market performance in the pigeon pea sector. Future research could explore the underlying factors contributing to these

dynamics and develop targeted interventions to improve market resilience.

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